

D2.8: Report on Governance Piloting Process

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Abstract:

One of the challenges encountered by the EOSCpilot project was to gather structured feedback from a wide variety of potential stakeholder about the ‘moving target’ that is the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). EOSC was at its early stage of construction, pilot proof of concept of services were constructed at the same time stakeholder mapping was performed and Governance was being designed by the project (and by the European Commission in parallel, providing a roadmap of EOSC present and future projects). This interaction of projects and initiatives was designed to conduct a fast-paced implementation of the EOSC, combining a top-down and bottom-up approach, where results from piloting the proof-of-concept provide input into the overall design.

In this context, this Report on Governance Piloting Process describes the methodology used for a structured bottom-up approach of EOSCpilot Work Package 2, and how it was used by the different tasks (Stakeholder mapping, Governance framework design, Rules of participation, Business model), contributing to the Governance Development Forum. In addition to traditional tools such as surveys, webinars, workshops and conferences, a specific tool with an interactive platform was used to gather audience feedback.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

*“Caminante, no hay camino, se hace camino al andar”
“Walker, there is no path, the path is made by walking”*

Antonio Machado, from "Proverbios y cantares"
in Campos de Castilla, 1912.

One of the challenges encountered by the EOSCpilot project was to gather structured feedback from a wide variety of potential stakeholder about the ‘moving target’ that is the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). EOSC was at its early stage of construction, piloting proof of concept of services were constructed at the same time stakeholder mapping was performed and Governance was being designed by the project (and by the European Commission in parallel, providing a roadmap of EOSC present and future projects). This interaction of projects and initiatives was designed to conduct a fast-paced implementation of the EOSC, combining a top-down and bottom-up approach, where results from piloting the proof-of-concept provide input into the overall design.

In this context, this Report on Governance Piloting Process describes the methodology used for a structured bottom-up approach of EOSCpilot WP2, and how it was used by the different tasks (Stakeholder mapping, Governance framework design, Rules of participation, Business model), contributing to the Governance Development Forum – see Figure 1. In addition to traditional tools such as surveys, webinars, workshops and conferences, a specific tool with an interactive platform was used to gather audience feedback.

Figure 1: WP2 (Governance) organisation

The results of these tasks were included in Deliverables and project outputs and eventually, to a large extent, have been taken into account or even adopted by the European Commission roadmap (see some of the principal document about EOSC implementation in Figure 2). A positive side-effect of this collective endeavour and interactive process was strong team-building among partners involved in co-creating this Governance scheme, who learned to work together across many scientific fields.

Figure 2: Covers of some of the principal document about EOsc implementation

1. INTRODUCTION

A specific challenge encountered by the EOSCpilot project, which started as an initial project of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) initiative, was to get structured feedback from a wide variety of potential stakeholder about ‘something’ which was not clearly described at the beginning of the project. EOSC was a moving target, where service prototypes were constructed at the same time stakeholder mapping was performed, and Governance was designed by the project as a co-creation activity. And, by the European Commission itself in parallel, providing a roadmap of EOSC present and future projects.

This ‘entanglement’ of projects and initiatives was designed to enable a fast-paced implementation, where early results from the piloting proof of concept provide feedback to the overall design. In this context, this Report on Governance Piloting Process is focused on the description of the methodology that was used by the Governance work-package of EOSCpilot, how the meetings were organised, how the feedback was collected, and how this was used.

Specific Deliverables provide detailed information on the many aspect of this action:

- D2.1: Draft Stakeholder Map¹, provided information about how we identified the major category of stakeholder, and members of these category that have been targeted to gather feedback, D2.7: Final Stakeholder map will update this map at the end of the project, including all stakeholder that have been identified during the project;
- D2.2: Draft Governance Framework for the European Open Science Cloud², provided a first Governance framework, including governance principles, structure and processes, that was presented to our stakeholder during specific meeting and at the Governance Development Forum meetings and webinars. After the process of collecting feedback from these stakeholder, and updated version presented within a final Deliverable D2.6;
- D2.3: 1st Report on Governance Development Board involvement and activity³, followed by D2.9;
- D2.5: Recommendations for a minimal set of Rules of Participation⁴, was a very important step to outlines a minimal set of Rules of Participation for Service Providers and Users in EOSC, based on bottom-up feedback from stakeholder collected during our process;
- D2.6: Governance framework for the European Open Science Cloud⁵, that should include all relevant elements from the other Governance WP tasks and other WPs to present recommendations for the full EOSC governance framework;
- D2.7: Final Stakeholder Map⁶ updates this map at the end of the project, including all stakeholder that have been identified during the project;
- D2.8: Report on governance piloting process, *this* Deliverable;
- D2.9: 2nd Report on Governance Development Forum involvement and activity⁷, that summarize in detail all the central activity from this work-package to put in place the Governance Development Forum; and
- D2.10: Mechanisms to align national investments relevant to the objectives of the EOSC⁸;

This deliverable presents the methodology used for combining the top-down and bottom-up approach, structured feed-back and official positions from major stakeholders, in conjunction with feedback from thematic workshops, and combines them with other official sources⁹ from European Commission. This complements the information provided in D2.9 on Governance Development.

¹ <https://www.eoscpilot.eu/content/d21-draft-stakeholder-map>

² <https://www.eoscpilot.eu/content/d22-draft-governance-framework-european-open-science-cloud>

³ This is a confidential report, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission), and is not yet publicly available.

⁴ <https://www.eoscpilot.eu/content/d25-recommendations-minimal-set-rules-participation>

⁵ <https://www.eoscpilot.eu/content/d26-governance-framework-european-open-science-cloud>

⁶ <https://www.eoscpilot.eu/content/d27-final-stakeholder-map>

⁷ <https://www.eoscpilot.eu/content/d29-2nd-report-governance-development-forum-involvement-and-activity>

⁸ <https://www.eoscpilot.eu/content/d210-mechanisms-align-national-investments-relevant-objectives-eosc-0>

⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/ec_rtd_eosc-main-background-documents_042019.pdf

2. EOSCPILOT GOVERNANCE PILOTING PROCESS

2.1. EOSCpilot Complexity

In this deliverable we will focus on presenting some specific aspects of the governance piloting process methodology, and on a specific tool - Slido¹⁰ - an audience interaction tool to gather feedback at meetings, events and conferences. It offers interactive Q&A, live polls and insights to refresh classical panel discussions. But, a tool is nothing without a hand, and without a will and intention. The use of this tool was motivated by the ambitious and complex goal of this this project and of this peculiar work-package, at the time it took place.

One of the difficulties of this work-package was to develop, in parallel, the Stakeholder mapping, the drafting of a Governance framework, the Rules of Participation (which have obvious impact on all other aspect of the Governance framework), along with financial aspects, also related to EOSC stakeholders mapping and role.

All this within an EOSC scope of offering ‘1.7 million European researchers and 70 million professionals in science and technology a virtual environment [...], across borders and scientific disciplines¹¹, and with the goal to promote Openness and FAIR¹² principles. While, in parallel, the European Commission was also working on such a plan, putting in place an independent High Level Expert Group¹³.

The [High Level] Expert Group operates in full autonomy and transparency. The views and recommendations in [their] report are those of the Expert Group members acting in their personal capacities and do not necessarily represent the opinions of the European Commission or any other body; nor do they commit the Commission to implement them.

Because of this complexity, it was clear that the classical ‘V-model’ of the systems engineering process could not be applied to achieve the goals (see Figure 3). Rather, a more agile and iterative process was required - which is why pilot projects, such as EOSCpilot, have been put in place. However, for the same reasons, the EOSCpilot project needed internal interaction and feedback. Draft ideas of what the EOSC could be needed to be presented to many stakeholders, to enable feedback to be collected and integrated, which could then be implemented into a revised draft, and so on.

Figure 3: “V model” from Clarus Concept of Operations 2009-07-05 at the Wayback Machine, Publication No. FHWA-JPO-05-072, Federal Highway Administration (FHWA), 2005.

¹⁰ <https://www.sli.do/>

¹¹ COM(2016) 178 final (2016), <http://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regdoc/rep/1/2016/EN/1-2016-178-EN-F1-1.PDF>

¹² FAIR data are data which meet standards of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/turning_fair_into_reality_1.pdf

¹³ Prompting an EOSC in practice: https://ec.europa.eu/info/publications/prompting-eosc-practice_en.

2.2. Stakeholder Management Principles

The principles of Stakeholder Management theory found their root in the work of R. Edward Freeman¹⁴, with a latter synthesis in 2010 encompassing a larger view of stakeholder¹⁵. Stakeholder Management is a theory of organizational management and business ethics that was built in opposition to the traditional, more narrow view of a company, the ‘shareholder’ view, that define the primary goal of a company as creating value for shareholder. In contrast, Stakeholder Management theory defines the goal of an organisation as managing its multiple interactions, in a complex environment, with its multiple so-called stakeholders, in order to create value to a wider spectrum of parties, including shareholders amongst others (see Figure 4). Managing these many shareholders is a condition for a sustainable growth of revenue, where this growth is not considered as the ultimate and unique goal. This has profound effect on the management of a company.

Figure 4: Typical stakeholders of a company, divided in internal and external stakeholders. Source Wikipedia Commons.

From this origin as a tool oriented toward Company management, Stakeholder Management theory has proved its usefulness in a wider area, including governmental and other public organisations along with NGOs. The theory offers a framework to characterise interaction with a wide spectrum of stakeholders, help stakeholder identification and prioritisation, understanding of stakeholder concerns and engaging in fruitful communication and interaction aimed at a mutual benefit - not always related to monetary exchange. It also includes within its framework the view of Government, that could act as funding body or as regulator. It also considers ‘the society’, that could be represented by NGOs, Nature Protections organisation or Citizen Science organisations.

It could also be the ‘whole society’, as for instance the general view that could be extracted from survey with regard to ‘Science’ at large. Or, a specific part of it such as Research Infrastructures. And, when mutual benefit can not be met at the appropriate level with all stakeholders, it allows at least a better understanding of legitimate concerns. One pitfall of this theory, deriving from its popularity, is to consider ‘everyone’ as a stakeholder. Therefore, a stakeholder consultation should be undertaken carefully, taking the range of stakeholders into account in a proper way, and considering stakeholders through their relation to ‘something’ (a company, a project, a consortium, a NGO), in our case through their potential relationship with a future operational EOsc.

¹⁴ Edward Freeman “Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach”, 1984

¹⁵ Edward Freeman, Jeffrey S. Harrison, Andrew C. Wicks “Stakeholder Theory: The State of the Art”, 2010

2.3. Application of Stakeholder Management Theory to EOSC Governance process

“The European Open Science Cloud presents a vision for a research data ecosystem in Europe which truly enables data-intensive science and interdisciplinary research.”

Jean Claude Burgelman Head of Unit B2, Open Data Policies and Science Cloud, DG RTD, European Commission

As part of the EC’s Digital Single Market initiative, the EOSC is being established with the aim of being used by a wide variety of scientific fields, if not by all areas of science. As such, it will need to interact with many stakeholders.

Digital Single Market (DSM): An area in which individuals and businesses can access and exercise online activities under conditions of fair competition, with a high degree of consumer and data protection, irrespective of their nationality or place of residence.

One of ten priorities of Jean-Claude Juncker, President of the European Commission

The EOSC is meant to contribute to the ‘3 O’ strategy of the DSM - Open access to publications, Open research data and Open science, and to accelerate transition to open innovation. In this context, EOSCpilot has engaged with a broad range of stakeholders, crossing borders and communities, to consult widely on the benefits and requirements needed for the adoption of an open and integrated approach to research within the EOSC.

For this purpose Stakeholder Management Theory would seem to be the perfect support for engaging with stakeholders, but the big issue is that users are not direct ‘stakeholders’, they are stakeholders with regards to a company or an organisation, with which they have a relationship, which is itself a ‘stakeholder’ within EOSC.

Being defined as Stakeholder of an ‘EOSC in construction’ is far less concrete, and engagement is more complicated. The first task of WP2 was Stakeholder scoping, to determine who is affected and need to affect the EOSC, and in conjunction with the Science Demonstrators of WP4, to organize and manage the involvement of these stakeholders. Whilst at the same time, designing use cases to help people construct a vision of what could be their role within a future EOSC.

One of the difficulties of this work-package was to develop, in parallel with the stakeholder mapping, a Governance framework, and the associated rules of participation, which have impact on all other aspects of the Governance framework. The rules will aim to define who will be ‘in’ and who will be ‘out’, who will actively contribute and who will act solely as a user, taking account that a user could be both a provider and consumer of EOSC services. In addition, the financial aspects of the Business Model of the EOSC and mechanisms to align national investments relevant to the objectives of the EOSC, needed to be considered (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: EOSCpilot WP2 Governance Outline

2.4. Stakeholder Scoping, Awareness Raising, Governance Drafting and Iterative Process

The first task was to scope the wide field of potential stakeholders, to determine who is affected and need to affect the European Open Science Cloud, and to organize and manage the involvement of these stakeholders. Deliverable D2.1: Draft Stakeholder Map, provided initial information about how we identified the major categories of stakeholder, and the members of these categories that were targeted to gather feedback. Deliverable D2.7: Final Stakeholder Map, provided an updated mapping of the stakeholder landscape.

This work was based both on desk research and on stakeholder feedback, and a comprehensive methodological approach. This included a presentation of the core assumptions behind the choice of different types of stakeholders, and a validation approach adopted to verify the validity of the empirical data collected in the course of the production of the deliverables related to this Work Package.

The investigation started by understanding the number and kind of stakeholders participating in European Research Infrastructures and e-Infrastructures as well as the nature of their participation. The key elements of the methodology used are as follows:

- Understanding the scope and objectives of EOOSC: these are derived from formal EC papers and particularly the European Research Policies;
- Range of infrastructures and services;
- European policy initiatives and projects;
- Desk research;
- Identification of key stakeholders for focused interviews;
- Commercial players and the EU value chain.

Several roles for stakeholders were identified, based on the different service layers, and we also described ten types of stakeholders – see Figure 6 and Annex C for a detailed description of stakeholders groups and roles.

Figure 6: EOOSC identified stakeholder categories

Existing e-infrastructures have been examined, i.e. GEANT, EGI, PRACE, EUDAT and OpenAIRE, as they were considered a starting point for reviewing the main stakeholders and governance models for EOOSC. We reviewed their governance models, which provide important information that can be exploited in defining the governance model for EOOSC. Influential stakeholders were identified at both national and EU level, by analysing the participation of EU organizations in Horizon 2020 infrastructure projects (both e-infrastructures and Research Infrastructure projects) and in FP7 infrastructure projects.

However, the initial interviews demonstrated that awareness about EOOSC was limited. Not only were the scope and objectives of EOOSC unclear to many stakeholders, several stakeholders were not even aware of EOOSC.

With so many stakeholders group, there was many points of view about what EOOSC should, and should not be. A key issue was not to capture all, or even to capture most, but to capture a sufficient variety of Stakeholder feedback. This included feedback on needs and requirements, to test hypothesis used by the project to draft the Governance framework, and especially to identify ‘poison pills’ that would reduce the inclusivity of the

EOSC to specific science communities. For example, by setting rules of participation that would be too restrictive for some of these communities. For this purpose, feedback at many levels was collected, using tools such as surveys and webinars, which are well suited to collect the ‘official’ position of some of the Stakeholders, especially those organisations that have an identified representative, including Member State research funding institutions.

Deliverable D2.5: Recommendations for a minimal set of Rules of Participation, reflected the very important step of defining a minimal set of rules of participation for service providers and users in EOSC, based on principles of openness, transparency and inclusiveness. These have been designed after an in-depth analysis of widely accepted working practices in already established European infrastructures and organisations. The primary rule of participation, that ‘EOSC services shall be registered in an EOSC compliant or compatible service catalogue visible to the global EOSC gateway’, was directly derived from the process of iterative consultations of EOSC Stakeholders, through the Governance Development Forum. Another step in this process, illustrated in Table 1 is the iterative alignment of EOSCpilot production with the EC Implementation Roadmap recommendations.

Figure 7 illustrates the iterative process and its link with Governance Forum and other stakeholders.

Figure 7: Illustration of an iterative process of EOSCpilot WP2

Statement number	Implementation Roadmap	EOScpilot recommended Rules of Participation
1	These rules would set out in a transparent and inclusive manner the rights, obligations and accountability of the different stakeholders taking part in the initiative (e.g. data producers, service providers, data and service users)	The analysis of 20the e-infrastructures and research infrastructures from June to September 2017 revealed various levels of entry barriers for Service Providers and Users, depending on the regulations of each individual infrastructure. High-barrier rules ensure a higher quality of Services, but also exclude many of them upfront. In turn, low-barrier rules enable the inclusion of most Services and empower the Users to select the Services according to their own criteria and needs. The consultation process started in October 2017 has already to refine the broad set of Rules of Participation initially gathered into a simple set that applies the lowest barrier of entry for service providers.
What the rules ought to address		
2	The use of the tools, specifications, catalogues and standards (EOsc shared resources) and applicable methodologies (framework for FAIR research data)	The rule No.1 states that "EOsc services shall be registered in an EOsc compliant or compatible service catalogue visible to the global EOsc gateway. In the EOsc compatible catalogues, the registered services must be described according to the appropriate EOsc service guidelines, which include information about the service availability, functionalities, operations, maturity, user support, interoperability (metadata schemata supported), openness (licenses), privacy (GDPR compliance), terms of use and contractual framework". Rationale: Inclusiveness, transparency, enabling standardisation and interoperability
3	The principles for regulating transactions in the EOsc (e.g. financial mechanisms and procedures, agreements/bylaws established by the EOsc governance framework)	The Specific requirement 2.2 states that "All EOsc services must have Terms of Use and/or Access policies displayed publicly online and/or via the EOsc Service catalogue(s). For example, for data catalogues, EOscpilot WP3 "EOsc policy" recommends to use machine readable licenses instead of terms of use (where possible) and to have a limited number of compatible licenses." Rationale: EOsc will build on services provided by many organisations. This may limit individual user access or the type of project that can use a given resource (e.g. data security). Such restrictions must be fully transparent.
4	The applicable legal frameworks (e.g. GDPR, copyright, Data Security and Cybercrime, dispute resolution and redress mechanisms, e-commerce directive)	The specific requirement 2.7 states that "Service providers should be transparent about the data management mechanisms they use to store-process-publish content. (e.g. Service Providers must publicly indicate if they offer the mechanisms to apply data protection rules according to the General Data Protection Regulation, especially in terms of Data Protection by Design and Data Protection by default, using relevant shields and information)". Rationale: Develop and maintain trust in provided services through transparency mechanisms.
Compliance with the rules could differ based on:		
5	The current situation and readiness of data infrastructures and services at the level of Member States (research infrastructures, e-Infrastructures) and disciplines (level of standardisation and integration) and the differences in their established rules and processes.	The specific requirement 2.6 states that "Service providers should adhere to a minimal set of quality guidelines that are being developed within the EOscpilot project (Task 6.2.4). Services that provide "Excellence-based access" (e.g. PRACE) - where research groups are allocated resources based on competitive processes - should operate with transparent expert peer-review". Rationale: Building trust with users. EOsc will build on services provided by many organisations. Users must be able to make informed choices based on quality, performance and capacity.
6	The actual existence and variety of service providers and the actual needs of users of the EOsc (e.g. public vs private; horizontal vs specialised).	See statement 1. Regarding access costs and charging model, the specific requirement 2.5 states that "Service providers may apply user charges/fees, which could vary by type of service, type of service provider and location of users. This information must be made clear to users online and via the service catalogue(s). Underlying costs could be indicated, e.g. for data-related services, service providers could indicate maintenance costs, curation, stewardship, etc." Rationale: Low barrier, as it allows for all players (public and private) to engage and the decision on what services to consume is left to users.
7	Evidence of changing needs and practices in relation with the implementation of the rules, in particular as concerns compliance with existing legal frameworks (e.g. GDPR) and emerging ones (e.g. free flow of data).	See statement 2.
8	The rules of participation of the EOsc would need to take into account the established practices and current needs of all researchers and service providers.	The rule No. 1 states that "There are multiple service catalogues in each scientific community (e.g. TeSS for life science training resources, bio.tools for bioinformatics resources, or FAIRsharing for data and metadata standards). It is recommended that service providers register their services to community accepted and supported catalogues."

Table 1: Alignment of the EOsc Rules of Participation with EC Implementation Roadmap

Deliverable D2.9: 2nd Report on Governance Development Forum involvement and activity, provide an extensive view of the activities performed to raise awareness and collect feedback, the central activity of WP 2. The following major types of activities were carried out over the two years of the project:

- Surveys: A questionnaire on ways to engage stakeholders in the development of the EOSC governance framework, along with audience interaction platform;
- Webinars: Ten monthly webinars were organized, reaching a total of 383 attendees;
- Workshops: Eight thematic workshops, targeting different stakeholder groups;
- A presentation at the EOSC Summit;
- A session on Governance at the Second Stakeholders Forum.

Figure 8: Examples of feedback and input received from EGDF activities and how they have been implemented in the WP2 work

In addition to these activities, feedback has been collected by making draft documents available for comment on the GitHub repository (especially for the D2.6 Governance framework)¹⁶.

This open comment process was needed to collect both official positions, and also the views of individual researchers, service providers and other ‘users’. This was to ensure a full bottom-up approach to complement the top-down approach. This was to help understand the specific issues and constraints of some communities that would restrict or prohibit them from using an EOSC. For example, though incompatibility with some of the rules of participation or with some element of the architecture design. As EOSC is as much a ‘change’ project as a ‘technical’ project, these discussions were intended to avoid a ‘flight of Icarus’ effect, burning our ‘wings’ when launching the project at scale. In a context of anxiety about funding, these discussions were appreciated, and helped to avoid rejection. For instance, it helped to explain that EOSC was not just another paradoxical injunction to do more with less, or a Trojan horse to cut costs and promote ‘more private sector everywhere’. These were some of the fears expressed to us ‘off the record’.

These discussions, both official and non-official, were useful to raise awareness, test the federated governance framework and sustainability plan, and implement corrective adjustment. Table 2 summarises events and activities carried out through the duration of the project.

¹⁶ See: <https://github.com/EuropeanOpenScienceCloud/Governance> and <https://europeanopensciencecloud.github.io/Governance/>

Table 2: Events and activities carried out

Time / Place	Event or Activity
13-31 March 2017	Survey: Ways to engage stakeholders in the development of the EOsc governance framework
6 April 2017	1 st EOsc Governance Development Forum webinar
4 May 2017	2 nd EOsc Governance Development Forum webinar
9 May 2017, Helsinki	EGDF workshop “Research Infrastructures perspectives on the governance of European Open Science Cloud”
5 July 2017	3 rd EOsc Governance Development Forum webinar
17 August 2017	4 th EOsc Governance Development Forum webinar
8 September 2017, Athens	EGDF workshop “Open science policy aspects in the context of EOsc governance framework”
14 September 2017	5 th EOsc Governance Development Forum webinar
2-3 October 2017, Tallinn	EGDF workshop “Drafting Governance Framework and Principles of Engagement for European Open Science Cloud”
12 October 2017	6 th EOsc Governance Development Forum webinar
9 November 2017	7 th EOsc Governance Development Forum webinar
25 January 2018, Porto	Workshop: “Piloting EOsc Governance Framework” at EUDAT Conference “Putting the EOsc vision into practice
15 May 2018	EOscpilot at E-IRG Workshop
16 May 2018	ENVRI Week’s EOscpilot Workshop
17 May 2018	8 th EOsc Governance Development Forum webinar
29 May 2018, Ljubljana	Workshop: “Recommendations on Governance and Rules of Participation”, PRACEdays / European HPC Summit Week 2018
11 June 2018, Pisa	EOsc Summit
18 September 2018	9 th EOsc Governance Development Forum webinar
9-11 October 2018, Vienna	Digital Infrastructures for Research
25 October 2018	10 th EOsc Governance Development Forum webinar
21 November 2018, Vienna	Governance Session at the Second EOscpilot Stakeholders Forum

2.5. Specific Tools Used for EOSC Governance Process

In support of the surveys, webinars, workshops and presentations we also used a simple audience interaction platform called Slido¹⁷. This allows the crowdsourcing of audience questions during presentations and webinars. Using mobile devices, participants can ask questions or vote on other people’s questions that they find interesting. During the Q&A sessions, the most popular and the most interesting, original questions were displayed on the presentation screen, allowing a lively discussion. Slido was also used to run live polls - see Annex B and **Error! Reference source not found.**). It was used at the Governance session at the Second EOSCpilot Stakeholders Forum (Vienna 2018) and also at the ‘Putting the EOSC vision into practice’ conference, organised by EUDAT, January 2018 in Porto (see Table 3). At the session on ‘Piloting EOSC Governance Framework’, attendees contributed to the design of the EOSC governance, in terms of model, principles of participation and business model. The process followed was to:

- Present a draft model for EOSC governance developed by the EOSCpilot project;
- Discuss important related aspects and open questions with participants;
- Collect feedback, suggestions and remarks, in order to progressively improve the model.

Figure 9: EOSC Stakeholders Forum, session on Governance, 21 November 2018, Vienna

Table 3: Main issues discussed in workshops

Issue	Further Explanation
Scope of EOSC and communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Should EOSC become a physical cloud infrastructure or a set of principles guiding a federated implementation (rules of engagement)? • A clear definition of what EOSC is. • Importance and role of the research infrastructures. • Use cases.
Governance and funding of EOSC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • These should be based on strong national coordinating building blocks. • Embed the practical advice of repository managers, IT service operators and researchers in the governance and operation of EOSC. • Governance model must take into account the incentives of researchers to share their data. • Synergies between research infrastructures and e-infrastructures. • Governance structure that involves stakeholders. • Compliance to GDPR and its national implementations. • To gather funders from member states together for a discussion.

¹⁷ <https://www.sli.do/>

Issue	Further Explanation
Acceptance of FAIR principles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HLEG report, and doubts relating to if the full research community or the research infrastructures will support the proposals in the report. • Sensitive data management and sharing (informed consent management, dynamic consent). • Sensitive data processing. • Interfacing and interoperability. • Data quality.

The responses also demonstrated that the workshops highlighted a diversity in perception on the actual scope of EOSC, in particular, between e-infrastructures and other research infrastructures. Thus, in order to turn the EOSC vision into a working implementation, the practical advice of repository managers, IT service operators and researchers needs to be embedded in the governance and operation of EOSC. Being able to manage practices, such as peer-review access have also been emphasised.

The following points were also raised:

- Researchers want to use computing at local, national and European level. The interface from EOSC is interesting: ‘single-stop-shop with all the interfaces is something we cannot do without’. For users, the research community-specific services are equally important as computing, both should be part of EOSC. Services really have to work if they are to be used. The provenance of data is very important;
- Barriers: Policy on network layer, issues when transfer data between private providers using the research network (GÉANT);
- Agreement must be reached between service providers on the types of information to be shared about users;
- How does EOSC benefit researchers? Funders must be the drivers of EOSC development, otherwise infrastructures may be reluctant to develop their services towards compatibility with EOSC (optimal use of the scarce resources);
- Branding EOSC for researchers, and to pay attention to how information about EOSC is disseminated. Aim to get researchers to ask for EOSC services;
- Raising awareness of EOSC: What, when and how should this be communicated to different stakeholders?

Some other concerns have also been reported, such as:

If open science practices are required, at the same time as researchers continue to be judged, measured and rewarded by the number of publications in high impact factor venues, disjoint and distrust will develop within the academic community.

Position paper: A Vision for Open Science¹⁸

At this stage, even if all the identified stakeholders (see Figure 6) have not yet provide structured comment on the EOSC, we consider that all groups who can affect or are affected by the EOSC have been given the opportunity to comment and input into the development of decisions.

¹⁸ From Michael Ball, Margreet Bloemers, David Carr, Valentino Cavalli, Maria Haglund, Vasso Kalaitzi, Elli Papadopoulou, Paola Quattroni, Dale Robertson, Jadranka Stojanovski, Marta Teperek, Yasemin Türkyilmaz-van der Velden, Karen Vandeveld. Editing & Design: Friedel Grant. This document elaborates on the outcome of the workshop Research Institutions and Libraries and the role of Funders in EOSC, held at the LIBER 2018 Conference in Lille, France and organised by LIBER as part of the EOSCpilot project. See: <https://www.eoscpilot.eu/content/report-vision-open-science>

2.6. Output on Governance Framework for the European Open Science Cloud

Deliverable D2.6: Governance framework for the European Open Science Cloud, made recommendations for the full EOSC governance framework, based on all relevant elements from the other tasks within the Governance Work Package, and from other Work Packages within EOSCpilot. It outlines a three ‘layer’ stakeholder driven governance framework for the long-term management and oversight of the EOSC, which has been developed in consultation with key stakeholders, using the process outlined in this report – see Figure 10.

The **Stakeholder layer** would allow the stakeholders to determine the requirements, policies and principles of engagement, and make proposals to the Strategic Layer on how these could be met.

The **Strategic layer** would review, agree and prioritise these proposals and requirements to form the strategic vision and objectives of the EOSC.

The **Executive layer** would be responsible for ensuring that the EOSC meets this vision and these objectives by:

- Commissioning Core resource as required;
- Commissioning new Supported resources as required;
- Ensuring that Supported services are properly compensated;
- Ensuring that the resources within EOSC are both compliant and meet the strategic objectives.

The Stakeholder layer would also communicate to the Executive about how well the EOSC is meeting stakeholder requirements at an operational level, and the Executive would report this against the strategic objectives to the Strategic layer.

Figure 10: Governance Decision Flow

3. CONCLUSIONS: FROM OBLIVION TO EXISTENCE

“EOSCpilot has defined the scope of the EOSC and has gotten off the ground what originally did not exist before. Now, it is launched and this is because of projects like yours,”

Jean Claude Burgelman Head of Unit B2, Open Data Policies and Science Cloud, DG RTD, European Commission, Second EOSC Stakeholders Forum, Vienna, November 2018.

It is beyond the scope of this report to draw conclusions about the whole work of EOSCpilot project; however, some lessons can be learned from the methodology that was used for the Governance Piloting activity. EOSCpilot devised a number of activities and work strands to challenge both the research community and a wider range of stakeholders, to reflect and provide feedback on the development of the EOSC.

The EOSCpilot Governance Piloting activity has been an integral part of the project and a challenge in itself. It has explored novel methods and approaches to raise awareness, foster interaction with stakeholder and gather their input via a variety of meetings and online consultations over the period of the project:

- Surveys: A questionnaire on ways to engage stakeholders in the development of the EOSC governance framework, along with an audience interaction platform;
- Webinars: Ten monthly webinars were organized, reaching a total of 383 attendees;
- Workshops: Eight thematic workshops, targeting different stakeholder groups;
- A presentation at the EOSC Summit;
- A session on Governance at the Second EOSCpilot Stakeholders Forum.

After a careful process of the identifying stakeholders and their potential role, and designing proper rules of participation, a variety of methods were used to interact with stakeholders. This allowed a robust trial of a draft Governance model, and an iteration of drafting and testing, to eventually converge on a three-layer Governance model (Strategic, Executive and Stakeholder).

Part of this iterative process was to organise regular alignment of developing EOSCpilot proposals with the European Commission recommendations. These results have been injected in to a number of deliverables and project outputs, and have influenced the EC whitepaper on EOSC, ‘Commission Staff Working Document: Implementation Roadmap for the European Open Science Cloud¹⁹. The endorsement of EOSCpilot findings was then confirmed at the EOSC Stakeholder Forum in Vienna, November 2018.

This report has presented how the governance piloting methodology has facilitated these trials of the governance framework under development, through testing ideas and concepts on a number of stakeholder groups. It has also presented the strong challenge of having at the same time to (a) scope the potential stakeholders of EOSC, (b) provide them awareness of ‘what could be’, and collect their feedback in a bottom-up approach, whilst (c) taking into account top-down feed-back, with a series of iterations allowing people to ‘think fast and slow²⁰ about what is inherently a change management activity.

And, EOSC is change management at an unprecedented scale, to promote open science at the European level, involving the full spectrum of research related organisations, service providers, research infrastructures and government agencies through to individual businesses and citizen scientists.

Finally, one positive side-effect of this very interactive process of getting people from different areas to work together, was to build a strong team amongst the partners involved in co-creating this Governance scheme. It also demonstrates, in a very concrete way, that we were stronger and smarter together, as none of this would have been achieved without using our different skills, cultures and background toward the achievement of a common goal.

¹⁹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/swd_2018_83_f1_staff_working_paper_en.pdf

²⁰ Harvard Business Review June 2011, “Before you make that big decision”, D. Kahneman, D. Lovallo, O. Sibony.

ANNEX A. EVENT REPORTS

A.1. ESFRI RIs and EOSC Workshop London, UK – January 2019

ESFRI organised a workshop on the relationship between ESFRI Research Infrastructures (RIs) and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), in London on 30 January 2019 where EOSCpilot Coordinator Juan Bicarregui presented the current state of EOSC and where efforts are currently moving towards.

The main objective of the workshop was the liaison among ESFRI, ESFRI RIs and EOSC stakeholders, in order to ensure the optimal integration of ESFRI RIs in the EOSC ecosystem. In this direction, the Workshop aimed to:

1. Promote sharing existing good practices and experiences and collaborating on:
 - Open science policies, including domain/cross-domain ones;
 - Data and services' sharing and re-use, including the adoption of FAIR principles and the appropriate criteria for reproducibility of data and research results (+R);
 - Understanding strategies for federating into EOSC the good practices and services developed by the ESFRI RIs.
2. Understand, plan for and serve current and future ESFRI RIs requirements by:
 - Understanding and discussing the architecture, access, and interfaces;
 - Understanding and discussing the governance and participation rules ;
 - Planning training for developing skills.
3. Share ESFRI position on EOSC.

The workshop was hosted by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI/STFC) at the London Royal Geographical Society, supported by the StR-ESFRI Project (Support to Reinforce ESFRI), in cooperation with ESFRI and the European Commission, DG Research and Innovation (Unit B4 – Research Infrastructure).

A.2. Report - A Vision for Open Science

Funders are well positioned to shift the incentives for open science inherent in grant application processes and improve the way research is evaluated. Institutions can change the *status quo* by promoting and rewarding researchers' careers, and collaborating with research libraries in contributing to development of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) infrastructure, tools and relevant skills.

The workshop report²¹ elaborates on the outcome of the workshop 'Research Institutions and Libraries and the role of Funders in the European Open Science Cloud' held at the LIBER 2018 Conference in Lille, France. It sets a vision in which open science is the norm, and all funding bodies as well as institutions and researchers recognise the benefit of open science and embed best open science practice into their processes. The workshop was organised by LIBER as part of the EOSCpilot project.

A.3. How Research Institutions and Libraries can help deliver the EOSC

Survey amongst workshop participants at the LIBER workshop 'How Research Institutions and Libraries can help deliver the European Open Science Cloud', that took place during the IDCC18 Conference in February 2018. The audience was approximately 55 participants, composed of:

- Librarians 30%
- Data Professionals 23%
- Infrastructure Providers 13%
- Repository Managers 12%
- Researchers 10%

²¹ See <https://www.eoscipilot.eu/content/report-vision-open-science>

- Publishers 2%
- Other 10%

The single largest obstacle for institutions to start rewarding researchers based on Open Science criteria is 'senior leadership not convinced about Open Science', followed by 'not enough push from funders'. With a slightly lower score, the two most rated options were 'researchers not convinced about Open Science' and 'too much administrative burden to change processes'.

The biggest driver for institutions to reward researchers based on Open Science criteria for a very high majority is to make research grants available only to researchers committed to Open Science. The second highest-ranking driver is the financial threat by government and other funding bodies if they did not do so.

In most institutions, the management of Research Information System is spread across different departments. Only in 14% of the cases this is managed by the Library and in 12% by the individual research department. To monitor performance, institutions collect a variety of information on research outputs and research activities. The ones that score higher (15%-25%) are, in decreasing order:

- Grants/research funding acquired;
- Activities related to academic science communications (invited lectures, conference, presentations...);
- Bibliographic data or research publications activities related to popular science communication.

It is worth noting that only 10% of participants felt their institutions collect CRIS (or equivalent formatted) bibliographic data of research publications.

Participants Brainstorming Discussions

After the survey, participants split in four groups (covering the roles Managers of research Libraries at institutions, *Managers of research departments*, *Funding bodies* and *Local, national government agencies*), to discuss possible policy interventions related to the following topics:

- Incentives for researchers;
- FAIRness of research outputs;
- Data stewardship.

The output of the four groups can be summarised as follows:

Librarians

Participants in the workshop feel that libraries do not have real power in making policy decisions concerning incentives for researchers, but they can influence institutional Open Science policies in various ways. Thanks to their neutral stance and their intermediary position between researchers and institutions, they can effectively advocate for Open Science policies.

Research data management is changing the relationship between libraries and university administration and researchers. Besides building networks and collaborations within the university to influence RDM policy making, libraries can also influence the implementation of services and infrastructures. Libraries can also support researchers by providing a hub for information, best practice and advice, e.g. on funding opportunities, DMP writing, etc.

Libraries have an important role to play in supporting FAIRness of research outputs. They offer support and training to researchers on FAIR data management and best practice on data infrastructure and services, and can provide case studies showing the higher impact of FAIR and open data for research. They have the capability to translate between funder/university etc. requirements and researchers' needs.

Libraries can play a role in data stewardship by proposing services to the institutes and departments/faculties so they can decide how they want data stewardship to be organized.

Institutions

Research institutions can initiate/support the adoption of incentives that contribute to better, more open data management by promoting DMPs discussions around grant applications, this would help researchers with their grant application.

Institutions should help researchers understand the implications of good Data Management Planning and help them finding trusted solutions to convince them that opening up their data does not mean make it prone to misuse. Building DMPs into the CRIS system would improve the quality of research as well as the institution's ability to obtain relevant metrics.

Institutions can pursue many initiatives that provide incentives for researchers. They can improve local research standards by sharing DMPs more broadly within the institution and outside, by establishing dedicated data steward positions to help researchers, by making practical guidelines, case studies and support services available, encourage wider collaboration, by advocating Open Science practices especially with senior research leaders, trying to make them champions for younger researchers to follow. They could pilot new rewards for sharing data/making data reusable by other researchers, or point-based mechanisms for career progression.

Institutions can contribute better to the EOSC implementation by integrating the tools and the IT environment research have to operate in, making things easily interoperable, exportable and machine ready. Better ways of engaging with researchers should be explored, especially to get senior leading researcher aboard and help them embracing novelty. This group reached a similar conclusion as the National Agencies group, that there is a lot of inertia in the system and constant action is required to change the status quo.

Funders

Funding bodies have the option to provide incentives that contribute to better, more open data management by researchers. Workshop participants felt that funders should make Research Data Management more prominent in their agenda, and consistently provide guidelines/requirements that map onto EU policies, so that all researchers can benefit from a seamless environment regarding RDM.

To contribute to increase the FAIRness of research outputs, funders should include RDM-skilled reviewers in funding panels, or ensure that reviewers get trained on RDM, so that they can appropriately assess grant requests. They should consider providing financial incentives to open up the data as soon as possible and not only at the end of a project.

National Agencies

The availability of infrastructure is key. Workshop participants felt that funding infrastructure directly would make openness easier and fairer. National agencies can ensure greatest impact by making sure that only open/FAIR research gets grants.

There is a lot of inertia in the system and vested interests in the *status quo*. National agencies should promote actions at institutional level both in bottom-up and top-down direction, support for early education on the benefits of openness to researchers, and implement mechanisms that increase the benefits to the institution. Make information regarding publication openness statistics public.

More countries should follow on the establishment of a national co-ordinating role on data stewardship schemes, provide training, provide information and training resources.

A.4. ANNEX A4: EOSC training knowledge exchange at ELIXIR workshop in Berlin

The yearly All-hands meeting of ELIXIR²², the European intergovernmental organization that coordinates and develops life science resources across Europe, is a platform to exchange knowledge, experiences and ideas. At 2018 meeting in Berlin, a small workshop was dedicate to training activities around the use of life sciences

²² <https://www.elixir-europe.org/>

data and the associated infrastructure(s), and more explicitly, how to make training material FAIR (Findable Accessible Interoperable and reusable).

Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS), is the Dutch organisation involved in data management training activities at the national level, but also in the training work packages of EOSCpilot, EOSC-hub and OpenAIRE. DANS was invited, as an external participant and training expert, to join the ELIXIR workshop and share experiences on the “FAIRification” of training material within the scope of the EOSC developments and discuss how to define a skills commons for FAIR training and data stewardship.

Through two presentations the EOSC developments and experiences so far were shared and communicated. Especially the complementary relation between domain specific services and training provided by ELIXIR, and the more generic infrastructural training framework provided by EOSC, was a base for constructive discussions. All parties agreed to intensify the sharing of knowledge and ideas in the near future.

The results of the workshop, including the presentations are available online²³.

A.5. EOSC seeds planted in fertile DARIAH-EU earth

DARIAH, the pan-European Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities, is a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) and as such an important partner within the EOSC developments. At the DARIAH annual event 2018, the EOSCpilot and EOSC-hub projects were represented and presented in the poster session, and EOSC was frequently discussed in the plenary and thematic sessions built around the central theme of the meeting ‘Open Science’.

After the meeting, the DARIAH commitment to EOSC was clearly expressed through the position paper²⁴ published by the European Alliance for Social Sciences and Humanities (EASSH). This was published prior to the EOSC Summit, and expressed the vision of research networks in the humanities and social sciences like DARIAH, CLARIN and CESSDA.

The DARIAH network itself is committed to seeing that a broad disciplinary inclusion in EOSC becomes a reality, not just in words, and that the arts and humanities will take their place in the EOSC technical infrastructure and governance. To ensure this, DARIAH participates in the EOSC-Gov project Stakeholder Liaison Groups and in the consultation on the EOSC participation rules.

For a recap and the keynotes of the DARIAH “Open Science” meeting in Paris see the DARIAH YouTube presentations²⁵.

A.6. 2nd ASTERICS/OBELICS Workshop - Astronomy & Astroparticle Physics assists in building the European Open Science Cloud

Goal and objective

The workshop²⁶ took place in October 2017, organised by the **French CNRS LAPP laboratory**, and hosted locally by the **Institute for High Energy Physics of Barcelona**, one of the ASTERICS’ partners.

The second day of the workshop was dedicated to building bridges between **ESFRI projects, concerned scientific communities, e-infrastructures**, and further consortia, and to call them to action for the **implementation of the EOSC for data interoperability in the astrophysics** related disciplines.

²³ <https://www.elixir-europe.org/events/elixir-all-hands-2018>

²⁴ http://www.eassh.eu/PDF/EASSH_Open_Science_May2018_Fnl.pdf

²⁵ Recap: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3DeXluRH0HA>; Keynote Jon Tennant: ‘Open Science is just good science’ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UEEcwRUgQu8>; Keynote Teresa Scassa: ‘Intellectual Property Rights in Ethically Open Science’ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Udly8zTIhLO>

²⁶ <https://indico.astron.nl/conferenceDisplay.py?confId=87>

Members of the EOSC community such as EOSCpilot, EOSChub, EOSC HLEG representatives and ESFRI projects presented their key capabilities and explored possible commonalities and synergies between the two communities.

Takeaway messages

EOSC vision: EOSC could be defined as a system of systems made of existing and emerging RIs, e infrastructure, data repositories, registries etc. The system of systems approach should present certain features; the most important one is that EOSC will maintain an Operational and managerial independence. EOSC is not going to take over an existing infrastructure but to add value to it.

ESFRI for EOSC: The ESFRI community can actively support EOSC by leading synergies and cluster actions such as H2020-ASTERICS for the EOSC implementation in terms of **identifying common and coordinated approach to access HPC and open science resources**.

Furthermore, the ESFRI communities can play an active role in the EOSC **cross-disciplinary research challenge** by bringing researchers and scientist towards a common ground where they can work together and find solutions/services that can be used across different communities, in order to increase data interoperability and software reuse.

Call for actions

- EOSC should be a framework to bring together software tools, services, communities. EOSC should be sufficiently open to accept solutions developed or adopted or pre evaluated in the Cluster activities or other communities;
- EOSC should provide data-computing interoperability mechanisms to allow processing on archived data at the archive location (data centre);
- ESFRI should be considered as a building block towards the EOSC development in terms of FAIR data principles and software reuse;
- Through the H2020 ASTERICS project²⁷ the Astronomy and Astrophysics community can provide valuable inputs towards the EOSC implementation in terms of cross domain interoperability.

A.7. EOSC Stakeholder Forum 2017 Report²⁸ - Principles of Engagement in the EOSC

SESSION DRIVERS

The first consultations have led to proposing, as a basis for further discussion, one main Principle of Engagement for all service providers, accompanied by a series of domain-specific Principles.

Suggestion 1: The main Principle of Engagement for all service providers is that **EOSC services shall be registered in the appropriate EOSC Service catalogue**.

Suggestion 2: Domain-specific Principles allow to specify service description (availability, functionalities, maturity, support, terms of use, contractual framework, etc), as well as service requirements (quality & performance, sustainability, access policies, data portability, compatibility, etc). Seven specific Principles of Engagement were proposed for discussion:

- **Machine-readable metadata:** All services must include machine readable metadata and be identifiable by means of a common and persistent identification. Minimal information should be provided to the appropriate catalogue to allow users to assess the service providers (e.g. quality indicators, FAIR indicators, licences, etc).
- **Terms of Use/Access Policies:** All EOSC services must have Terms of Use and/or Access policies displayed publicly online and/or via the EOSC Service catalogue(s).

²⁷ <https://www.asterics2020.eu/>

²⁸ <https://www.eosc-pilot.eu/event/eosc-stakeholder-forum-28-29112017>

- **Portability:** The legal and technical infrastructure should enable the portability of data and services. Service providers (e.g. tools service providers) should enable the deployment and execution of their service by users in compatible cloud instance.
- **Access costs and charging model:** Service providers may apply user charges/fees, which could vary by type of service, type of service provider and location of users. This information must be made clear to users online and via the appropriate EOSC service catalogue. Underlying costs could be indicated, e.g. for data-related services, service providers could indicate maintenance costs, curation, stewardship, etc.
- **Quality of service:** Service providers should conform to the quality guidelines that are being developed within EOSC. Services that provide “Excellence-based access” - where research groups are allocated resources based on competitive processes - should operate with transparent expert peer-review.
- **Relation to users:** Service providers must convey information on data management mechanisms they use to store-process-publish content. If applicable, service providers:
 - Must publicly indicate if they provide the users with the means, and list them, to apply FAIR principles to research data;
 - Must publicly indicate if they offer the mechanisms, and list them, to ensure sustainability and reproducibility of data;
 - Must publicly disclose details on what data about users is collected and how the user statistics is tracked, managed and used for service improvement;
 - Must publicly indicate if they offer the mechanisms to apply data protection rules according to the General Data Protection Regulation, especially in terms of Data Protection by Design and Data Protection by default, using relevant shields and information;

All services must be accompanied by corresponding support and training material and possibly a helpdesk.

The panel discussion was driven by four questions:

1. Do you agree with the lightweight and inclusive approach with minimum service specifications, and add incentives to promote EOSC values/principles over time?
2. Which minimal set of information would you need to select/consume an EOSC service ?
3. Which additional principles would be key for you & your community?
4. From your point of view, is the proposed approach suitable for promoting open science?

TAKEAWAY MESSAGES

Andrew Smith (ELIXIR): there is a high level of variation that needs to be taken into account by the Principles of Engagement. Variation in:

- Services provided (EU projects, permanent services).
- Organisation type and permanence (Research Infrastructures / Projects).
- How service providers are integrated.
- How services run by providers are evaluated/monitored.
- Pricing policies.

This leads us to expand the consultation to a larger number of stakeholders, in particular Research Infrastructures via clusters. Additional input is also required from users to include industry.

Damien Lecarpentier (EUDAT) suggested generic concepts:

- EOSC needs to be open to all players.
- Principles of Engagement define the conditions to participate.
- Possibility of several catalogues or one single, and internal (core) services (See section 4.2.3 of the draft governance framework document (D2.2)).
- The catalogue(s) should be inclusive:
 - Service providers could offer certain services under EOSC;

- Services should be described in a standardised and transparent way.
- Some services could be further promoted (e.g. as EOSC+ services).

Jorge Sanchez (European e-Science Services Gateway - eInfraCentral):

- Challenges of cataloguing: Diverse vocabulary, various standards, level of adoption of SM practices, different processes to manage service portfolios, different maturity, numerous ways of representing services to the users on the web, no adopted APIs for exchanging service-related information, status of service catalogue of RIs: diverse and varying in several ways.
- Need: a common reference model (vocabulary, structures related information about service related information, harmonized views on service representations, functionality on the service gateway, common approach to automated processes for harvesting service related data, common approach to service performance monitoring).

Conclusions to the panel discussion:

- Principles of Engagement have to take into account an environment of multiple catalogues/registries.
- Technical interoperability is already taking place in many different projects.
- The Principles of Engagement must serve the communities needs, in particular domain-specific Research Infrastructures' needs.
- The Principles of Engagement should include specific requirements related to "People-as-a-Service".
- Importance of the role of portability between the services.

A.8. EOSC Stakeholder Forum 2017 Report - Interoperability in practice & FAIR data principles

SESSION DRIVERS

Creating the EOSC will depend strongly on the ability to connect infrastructures and data and to make them accessible to the community at large in a seamless fashion. Although this goal seems to be commonly accepted, there are lots of questions remaining how infrastructure and data interoperability can be achieved on a large scale.

The aim of the session was to:

- Give a short update on the status of the EOSC Pilot activities on interoperability
- Get the view from high-profile and high-impact stakeholders that are not necessarily already participating in the EOSC pilot on difficulties to achieve an interoperable EOSC
- Derive opinions on what has to be done with highest priority in order to make progress
- Provide information on how the EOSC vision is accompanied by national initiatives

Two panel discussions were organised:

1: 'E-infrastructure interoperability' with Cristina Duma (INFN / CNAF), Licia Florio (GEANT), and Laurent Crouzet (French ministry MESRI).

Questions:

- What are the major challenges for e-infrastructures and research infrastructures to be part of an EOSC architecture?
- How does the connection of e-infrastructures in the EOSC context correlate with similar efforts on the national level?
- What advantages do you expect from the EOSC that will be worth doing the effort of the interoperability?
- What should be the next step and/or what is the most urgent action needed to progress towards infrastructure interoperability?

2: ‘Data interoperability’ with Françoise Genova (Univ. Strasbourg, RDA), Donatella Castelli (CNR), Carole Goble (Univ. Manchester, ELIXIR), Andrew Treloar (Monash University), Luiz Bonino (GO FAIR).

Questions:

- What are the synergies between EOSC and RDA (for Françoise) and GO FAIR (for Luiz)?
- What actions are taken in the context of FAIR data in your countries (for Carole, Andrew, and Donatella)?
- What should be the next step and/or what is the most urgent action needed to progress towards data interoperability in EOSC?

TAKEAWAY MESSAGES

The two panels had lively discussions, and we list here some key statements that were made:

e-Infrastructure and research infrastructure interoperability:

- There are technical challenges, but political and social challenges seem to be more important in the task to achieve interoperability.
- Particular challenges are governance and long-term sustainability.
- Some concern was raised that some ESFRIs might want to maintain their own environment and way of working, which might make their integration in EOSC more difficult.
- Next steps should be to define a catalogue of services and to demonstrate their quality and purpose for the different communities.
- The governance structure of the EOSC might have to be decided before member states and large infrastructures are able to fully engage into the EOSC.
- Building the EOSC should take into account recommendations of the European Interoperability Framework (EIF).

Data interoperability:

- FAIR awareness has to be raised — at researcher level there is little knowledge about FAIR and about the goals of the EOSC.
- Many initiatives to become more FAIR and to align with the EOSC are already ongoing on the national level.
- This is an opportunity but also an issue in view of the fact that the EOSC is not yet fully defined.
- For a successful and FAIR EOSC it is necessary to work closely together and to integrate activities from RDA, GO-FAIR, OpenAire, and other data interoperability efforts.
- When thinking about the EOSC, it is important to think globally but to act locally with researchers.
- Agreements should be bottom up: first within research domains, then across domains, with real use-cases for interdisciplinarity.
- Standardisation and guidelines are key for a successful EOSC.
- The end user lacks a “Facebook experience”, i.e. easy to use portals, added value, etc.

CALL FOR ACTIONS

The EOSC (pilot) seems to have a communication issue and it is important to pass the message to the researchers and other stakeholders:

- What the general goal of the EOSC is.
- That the EOSC has not yet been fully defined and not been implemented.
- That the EOSC is an evolving program and thus there is still time to influence how it is going to be put into place.
- Provide a catalogue of services foreseen to be part of the EOSC to demonstrate its added value.

The EOSC pilot should provide as soon as possible working examples that give users a 'FaceBook' experience, i.e. something with added value, easy to use, visually inviting.

A.9. EOSC Stakeholder Forum 2017 Report - Soap box session for Intermediaries, Research communities & Libraries

SESSION DRIVERS

The driver for the session was to allow stakeholders from research performing organisations, academic institutions and research libraries to discuss amongst themselves some key elements of Open Science and the way the EOSC enables them. Most of the session participants belonged to organisations that do not participate directly in the EOSCpilot project.

TAKEAWAY MESSAGES

Very valuable input was provided by this group. It was collected and filtered and is structured below according to the questions asked.

1. Vision

1.1 Characteristics of the EOSC that will make the difference to what is available today

- The EOSC is an infrastructure to support open science, bringing together existing, fragmented infrastructures in a federated and decentralized way, driven by researchers needs.
- It enables access, sharing and reuse of various research outputs, not just data, creating many new opportunities for multidisciplinary dialogue and collaboration.
- To make the difference to what is available today, the EOSC should create a culture of openness and should promote career rewards and incentives for open behaviours.
- The EOSCpilot should communicate more to researchers. It should better express and demonstrate benefits of openness, and ensure researchers are aware of the various tools and platforms that already exist.
- The EOSCpilot activities go in the right direction but some important economic factors and players, such as those related to the publishing, hardware and software industries, seem to be missing.

1.2 How open should EOSC be?

- Openness is not unconditional. Access to research outputs should be freely available to all, but issues related to the business models need to be addressed.
- The EOSC should be "as open as possible, as closed as necessary". This means that there may be variable levels of openness, in service and SLA, in data, in rules of participation, etc.
- For the EOSC to be effective it needs to coordinate/cooperate with all other organizations involved in RDM – e.g. Liber, OpenAIRE, Research Data Alliance, EUDAT, etc.

1.3 How will EOSC support multidisciplinary research? How to enable this?

- By bringing libraries into communications – although library shouldn't be the only player in bringing the message into the university.
- Support generic metadata, ontologies, standardised metadata sets.
- Promote skills on data stewardship, as well as IT and technical skills starting from schools and up to higher education.
- Train the trainer.
- Raise awareness: provide case examples, best practices exchange, address societal challenges.

2. The EOSC will create an environment for researchers to be effective in publication dissemination, long-term preservation and reuse, etc. How do you see your role as users/enablers in fostering the uptake of the FAIR principles in your environment?

- Research Institutions and Libraries are enablers. They develop and support institutional policies and tools that promote and encourage FAIR principles. They see the need to provide incentives to FAIRness of research results. Support interoperability and data stewardship. They can act as point of contact.
- Universities support levels of compliance to FAIR principles and provide skills and practical guidelines for their application in concrete cases.
- All stakeholders should contribute to cultural change, raising awareness, and stress benefits to productivity from applying FAIR principles.
- EOSC could provide sandbox training environments that can be employed during institutional training exercises. Include FAIR in training. Build on MANTRA training courses.
- Bring research councils on board (not yet the case in every EU country). Funders to require verifiable and actionable DMPs.

3. Can you think of effective alternatives to the current evaluation and reward systems and how would you see your role as users/enablers in advocating for the establishment of alternative incentives?

The group identified some of the main barriers towards Open Science, namely:

- Losing control of data and not being credited
 - Allow for citability of data
 - Traceability of access – link to usage
 - Same for software
- Open to misuse and misinterpretation

The following incentives have been mentioned:

- Evaluation of “research objects” (publication+data+network) not just publications
 - Work on next generation metrics to continue and to balance several criteria/indicators including research integrity, Nagoya, and many other indicators
- Reward also scientific negative results
 - Make it easy for researchers to cite publications and data (DOI)
 - Make negative results citable and discoverable
- Put weight on data management plans, open APIs and open formats. Make these mandatory for research funding.
- Make Data Management Plans effective – check during performance of research
- Incentivise behaviours and outputs that build transparent processes.

Other recommended initiatives at various levels include:

- Need evaluation panels. Funders and learned societies have a crucial role to play in this respect.
- National rankings of institutional data openness – will encourage universities to encourage researchers
- Publishers can make it mandatory that data is made available
- Harness the enthusiasm of younger researchers.

Open Science is not another sort of science, is yet another aspect of current science. Don't oppose open and excellent science, excellent science and open science is the same thing, so discussion is needed what this means in a specific discipline – what is the actual impact of open science at the operational level (actual research process). Some people did not understand the relevance of this question for the EOSC.

4. Role of Research Producing Organisations, Academic Institutions and Research Libraries in promoting and supporting the EOSC take up?

Organisations in this group play an intermediary role. They act as liaisons, brokers, enablers of semantic interoperability and linked open data, trainers, curators.

Some participants challenged the question and wanted to discuss how the EOSC helps institutions rather than the other way around.

CALL FOR ACTIONS

It was suggested that:

- We need to define more clearly what the EOSC is, to explain better to this group of stakeholders how it is different from other organizations/infrastructures.
- The EOSC Websites needs to make very clear and prominent what the EOSC can offer to researchers. Universities need to understand clearly what it offers before they will promote it.
- The EOSC needs clear contact points in each country who can explain what it can do.

A.10. OSFAIR 2017²⁹ - FAIR metrics – Starring your data sets: A lightweight FAIR data assessment tool

The FAIR data principles – data should be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable – have rapidly gained a wide support, but to operationalise, measure and implement them appears to be no unambiguous task. Interestingly, the FAIR principles bear a great resemblance to the principles underlying the CoreTrustSeal (CTS), formerly known as the Data Seal of Approval (DSA) for trustworthy data repositories: data can be found on the internet, data are accessible, data are in a usable format, data are reliable, and data can be referred to. Although the latter two CTS principles have no direct equivalent in FAIR, the two sets of principles complement each other very well: the CTS can be used to assess the quality of repositories, FAIR the fitness for use of datasets.

DANS is The Netherlands institute for permanent access to digital research resources. In its long-term research data repository it currently preserves more than 36.000 data sets. Complementary to several initiatives to make new data FAIR, DANS is interested in assessing the level of FAIRness of extant data: in its own holdings as well as in other data repositories. Therefore DANS has started working on a practical operationalisation of the FAIR principles³⁰. The approach taken is such that the F, A, I and R can be measured independently, meaning that a rating of a dataset under one principle is independent from ratings under one of the others. Actually, it appeared that the principles defined under R better fit or are already covered by F, A, and I. In the DANS approach therefore the level of Reusability follows from the scores on the other principles. Please refer to this blogpost for more details³¹.

DANS has built an online tool prototype which guides the user through a set of questions – no more than five per F, A, and I – to assess a specific dataset. In the Open Science FAIR workshop more than thirty colleagues from universities, publishers and international projects have explored this so-called FAIRdat tool prototype³² themselves. Overall, the participants responded very positively to the tool: they found it easy to use and everything was explained (for each question the tool provides guidance). One participant even answered the question what was best with “that it exists”.

Understandably, there were also recommendations on how to improve the prototype. An important one concerns the target group or groups of such an assessment tool, because it requires some intimacy with the dataset under assessment. During the workshop the testing was carried out with datasets formerly unknown to the participants, and about a third of them reported that they didn't feel really capable and qualified to assess the datasets. Envisioned target groups for FAIRdat are archivists or data managers of the repository where the dataset is preserved (9 votes from the 17 attendants who used the online feedback questionnaire),

²⁹ <https://www.eoscpilot.eu/event/osfair-2017>

³⁰ <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

³¹ <http://blog.ukdataservice.ac.uk/fair-data-assessment-tool/>

³² <https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/fairdat>

someone who used the data (8/17) and the person(s) who created the dataset (6/17). A valuable suggestion was also to provide different views and perhaps different routes through the tool for different roles.

A few attendants fed back on the length of the underlying documentation; maybe role-specific variants could be the way to go. Interestingly, we learned that the question about a “clear and accessible data usage licence” needs more guidance and probably discussion within the community: does a copyright marker count as a licence in this sense? It was also noted that some questions asked by the tool are hard to answer when one hasn’t downloaded the data: file formats, for instance, are a crucial aspect of interoperability of the data, but they can be “hidden” inside .zip files. Also it was recommended to consider whether for some question a scale could be better than the current Yes/No questions.

As in other settings where the FAIRdat tool is being tested, opinions differed on interpreting Reusability as the resultant of the F, A, and I. Several participants fed back that it makes sense, but others are unsure or against it. DANS invites everyone to submit data characteristics that really need to be covered under the R.

Finally, DANS envisions that FAIRdat produces FAIR badges that the repository can show together with the dataset, indicating the level of FAIRness of that dataset. The majority of attendees who fed back (11/14) considers such badges “Great, that helps me decide if I’m interested in the data”. The main recommendation therefore is for DANS to proceed with this approach.

Authors: Peter Doorn, Elly Dijk and Marjan Grootveld, Data Archiving and Networked Services/DANS

A.11. OSFAIR 2017 - How FAIR Friendly is your data catalogue? Exposing FAIR data in EOSC³³

Introduction

Research communities and specially research infrastructures are making a concerted effort to homogenize, collect their (meta)data and publish them in the open through community specific data catalogues. This is a good start towards making data FAIR, but how can we ensure availability of domain specific FAIR data and data-analysis services through a common virtual research environment like the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)? From vertical domains (e.g., research infrastructures) to horizontal approaches (e.g., OpenAIRE, DataCite) which cover national settings and libraries/repositories, we see different content, data models, interfaces, frameworks, architectures and vocabularies being used.

The EOSCpilot data interoperability task aims to establish principles, propose recommendations and demonstrate how FAIR data hosted by domain specific data repositories and catalogues can be exposed to EOSC to be used and reused by EOSC services, repositories and users.

Goal, objectives and structure

The workshop had the goal to provide an update of the activities of the EOSCpilot data interoperability working group and engage different stakeholders to shape the work of this group. This workshop was a follow-up of the BlueBridge workshop³⁴ held on April 3 at the RDA meeting. The workshop was structured into two sessions. In session 1, scene setting presentations on EOSC were followed by short presentations by eight data catalogues representing subject-specific and generic systems and a review of a previous meeting. Prior to this workshop the organisers conducted a survey of 11 data catalogues and an early analysis was presented in session 2 followed by extensive breakout discussions of 13 principles of Data Catalogue metadata exposure and interoperability.

Outcomes

The participants got an overview of EOSC, the EOSCpilot project and the direction and scope of the EOSCpilot data interoperability working group. The presentations, the survey and the discussions contributed with

³³ <http://tinyurl.com/osf-eosc-datacat>

³⁴ <http://www.bluebridge-vres.eu/events/bluebridge-workshop-fair-friendly-research-data-catalogues-how-far-are-we-3-april-2017>

feedback to the group about how data catalogues can contribute to make FAIR data available into EOSC. The overall workshop contributed to define a set of principles that will drive the work of the EOSCpilot data interoperability working group and the recommendations we will proposed for EOSC.

ANNEX B. EXAMPLE OF SLIDO INTERACTIVE POLL, 25 APRIL - 31 MAY 2018

Piloting EOSC Governance Framework

25 Apr - 31 May 2018

Poll results

slido

Table of contents

- Warm up: What is your domain?
- 1) Do you agree with the 3 layers: Steering (users and providers); Strategic (funders and decision makers, including those at national level), and Executive?
- 1) The Steering layer should provide strong guidance and direction to the Strategic layer, the final decision-making body. The potential terms for this layer ("Advisory" vs. "Steering") are contentious: have you a better suggestion to term this layer?
- 1) Do you agree that both providers and consumers should be represented in the same layer (given that many communities will perform both roles)?
- 1) Do you agree with the decision flow and responsibilities between the 3 layers (Steering, Strategic, Executive)?
- 3) Do you think that the structure proposed would work for the Stakeholder forum?
- 3) The proposal is currently a skeleton outline, do you have any proposals on how to determine the details of this skeleton, in particular, how to involve the community in developing the details?

slido

Table of contents

- 5) Do you agree with our strategy: lightweight and inclusive approach with minimum service specifications, and add incentives to promote EOSC values/principles over time?
- 5) Which minimal set of information would you need, to select/consume an EOSC service ?
- 5) Which additional principles would be key for you & your community?
- 5) From your point of view, is the proposed approach suitable for promoting open science?

slido

Multiple-choice poll

Warm up: What is your domain?

030

End user / Scientist

 10 %

Service provider

 60 %

Policy maker

 13 %

Funding agency

 0 %

European Commission

 0 %

Others

 17 %

slido

Multiple-choice poll

1) Do you agree with the 3 layers: Steering (users and providers); Strategic (funders and decision makers, including those at national level), and Executive?

0 2 5

yes

no

I don't know

slido

Open text poll

1) The Steering layer should provide strong guidance and direction to the Strategic layer, the final decision-making body. The potential terms for this layer (“Advisory” vs. “Steering”) are contentious: have you a better suggestion to term this layer?

0 1 6

- Tracing layer
- Countries or institutions like to keep their decision making, Advisory would be better
- husbanding
- Depends on what exact power the layer has....
- +1 stakeholders
- +1 for community
- Driver
- Stakeholders
- The Community Forum
- Community
- Stakeholder committee
- Steering is ok. Guidance too
- stakeholder forum
- What about staying stick to stakeholder layer?
- I'm OK with steering btw
- Guidance

slido

Multiple-choice poll

1) Do you agree that both providers and consumers should be represented in the same layer (given that many communities will perform both roles)?

0 2 5

yes

no

I don't know

slido

Multiple-choice poll

1) Do you agree with the decision flow and responsibilities between the 3 layers (Steering, Strategic, Executive)?

0 2 3

yes

no

I don't know

slido

Multiple-choice poll

3) Do you think that the structure proposed would work for the Stakeholder forum?

017

Yes

 35 %

No

 6 %

Needs to be improved

 59 %

slido

Open text poll

3) The proposal is currently a skeleton outline, do you have any proposals on how to determine the details of this skeleton, in particular, how to involve the community in developing the details?

007

(1/2)

- There should be an active approach to get requirements, also from groups like researchers, citizens. Perhaps the Steering layer could prevent dilution of requirements, by actively eliciting and asking for requirements? This would be important for innovation.
- Can we learn something from open source communities, e.g. Linux Community?
- Research can be more or less community ordered. The less ordered don't care or have no resources to care. Hence, if one really, honestly want to engage research in governance, one needs to focus on the well organised communities := e.g. ESFRI.
- At least a first step would

slido

Open text poll

3) The proposal is currently a skeleton outline, do you have any proposals on how to determine the details of this skeleton, in particular, how to involve the community in developing the details?

007

(2/2)

- be to have working groups between RIs and e-infras. And then they can involve their own communities.
- Well moderated Wikipedia-like forum
- Projects with recent results, multiple domains: fit them into the model; what is missing?
- Being about Open Science one should consider scientists and scientific questions crucial in this context. So (representatives of) scientists and scientific principles should have a strong influence on key decisions.

slido

Multiple-choice poll

5) Do you agree with our strategy: lightweight and inclusive approach with minimum service specifications, and add incentives to promote EOSC values/principles over time?

017

slido

Open text poll

5) Which minimal set of information would you need, to select/consume an EOSC service ?

010

- I cannot answer without knowing what kind of service we talk about
 - Standard certifications held by the provider,...
 - Price, reliability, availability (e.g. can it disappear without notice)
 - Adoption level
 - Supported APIs
 - Quality of service, training and support,
 - please look at the work already completed by e-infra central
- on this
 - Ease of use
 - Cost, availability, reliability
 - SLA, price.

slido

Multiple-choice poll

5) From your point of view, is the proposed approach suitable for promoting open science?

011

- Yes
- 0 %
- No
- 0 %

Going in the right direction, but it should be improved

100 %

slido

ANNEX C. EOSC STAKEHOLDERS AND RESOURCES

Through the EOSCpilot Engagement activities, we have established a range of different stakeholder who would participate in and would both benefit from and provide benefits to the EOSC³⁵. Any effective governance structure would need to involve and take input from all these stakeholders. The key classes of stakeholder identified with the community is outlined in Table 4.

Stakeholder Group	Description
Researchers	<p>The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) will offer Europe's researchers and science and technology professionals a virtual environment to store, share and reuse the large volumes of information generated by the 'big data' revolution. EOSC, as a functional embodiment of the European Cloud Initiative, will support data-driven innovation and contribute to the creation of a Digital Single Market in Europe. Science and industry will obviously benefit from these developments.</p>
Service Providers	<p>Service Providers are the heart of EOSC's value proposition</p> <p>Service Providers functioning nationally or at a larger scale, with commercial, non-profit or public status, can have 2 roles in the EOSC: builders or providers.</p>
Research Producing Organisations, Academic Institutions and Research Libraries	<p>Research producing organisations, Academic Institutions and Research Libraries will be the core users of the European Open Science Cloud.</p> <p>Research libraries, archives, academic institutions, university departments and, generally, organisations that are significantly involved in promoting, supporting and enabling research-production activities, play an essential role in the research and scholarship ecosystem</p>
Learned Societies, Research Communities, Scientific and Professional Associations	<p>Learned societies, research communities, scientific and professional associations are key allies to build, use and promote the EOSC</p>
Enterprise	<p>Enterprises relate to the EOSC in multiple ways. EOSC's target group is categorized into a wide range of categories such as Small and Medium sized (SMEs), large enterprises, dynamic European start-ups and entrepreneurs-to-be, researchers, developers, deployers, providers, distributors, etc. Additionally, many sectors can benefit or contribute to the EOSC, for example healthcare, transportation, energy, manufacturing, education, analytics, etc.</p>

³⁵ Detailed in "D8.2: Stakeholder Identification & Engagement Strategy Plan." D8.2 is a confidential report and is currently only available to members of the EOSCpilot Consortium and the Commission.

Stakeholder Group	Description
Research Infrastructures	<p>The notion of Research Infrastructures refers both to traditional large physical installations, as well as to distributed facilities which “include networked resources and skill / capacity building initiatives. These resources use advances in information and communications technology and the big data revolution to underpin new collaborative methods of research”.</p> <p>Research infrastructures may be based at a single location, distributed across several sites and organisations, or provided via online platforms. Europe hosts several large-scale research infrastructures operating across national boundaries.</p> <p>Research Infrastructures are the base on which the future federated EOSC will be built. They provide several types of services to the EOSC, including data services and expertise. Research infrastructures are often very experienced in providing cloud services to researchers, and as such, are key players in the specification and the set-up of the EOSC. Close cooperation with other research infrastructures and e-Infrastructures within the EOSC will increase the capability of research infrastructures to combine and integrate data and resources in a common environment.</p>
E-infrastructures, VREs and other pertinent H2020 projects	<p>E-Infrastructures, VREs and other H2020 projects are key building blocks of the European Open Science Cloud</p> <p>The EC Digital Single Market refers to E-Infrastructures as ways of addressing needs of European researchers for digital services in terms of networking, computing and data management. They foster the emergence of Open Science and support the circulation of knowledge in Europe online and therefore constitute an essential building block for the European Research Area.</p> <p>Virtual Research Environments (VRE) help researchers from all disciplines to work collaboratively by managing the increasingly complex range of tasks involved in carrying out research on both small and large scales, and consists of the tools and technologies needed by researchers to do their research, interact with other researchers (who may come from different disciplines, institutions or even countries) and to make use of resources and technical infrastructures available. Some examples of VREs are EVER-EST³⁶, a VRE for research on Earth-science; VRE4EIC³⁷, supporting a multi-disciplinary approach to research on climate change and energy sustainability; D4Science³⁸, a Data Infrastructure hosting over 100 VREs; and BlueBridge³⁹, a gateway to over 60 VREs.</p>

³⁶ <https://ever-est.eu/>

³⁷ <https://www.vre4eic.eu/>

³⁸ <https://www.d4science.org/>

³⁹ <http://www.bluebridge-vres.eu/>

Stakeholder Group	Description
General Public / Citizen Scientists	<p>The EOSC project will create a cross-border and multi-disciplinary open innovation environment with the aim of delivering its benefits to citizens as well. Democratisation of science and open access to scientific data are indirectly providing their beneficial results to civil society. The activities and achievements of the EOSC and open science initiatives need to be linked with the everyday challenges, that citizens are sensitive to, such as public investments, new services and new job opportunities.</p>
National, Regional or Local Government Agencies	<p>Public authorities and government agencies, specifically in their capacity as organisations performing monitoring activities and using research, shall be able to fully exploit the possibilities around Big Data as EOSC will allow them to move, share and reuse data seamlessly across European borders, among institutions and analytical facilities and between different research and data disciplines</p>
Research Funding Bodies	<p>Research funding bodies are key stakeholders for the development of the EOSC. In recognition of this, they were among the first to be involved in extensive discussions with the European Commission's High-Level Expert Group in 2016 with a view to contribute to the initial recommendations on the realization of the EOSC.</p> <p>Several bodies at the European level make research grants available to researchers regardless of their nationality or field of research. This includes programmes supported by the EU under the Research and Innovation Framework programmes – including for example the direct actions of the Joint Research Centre, or the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions or the actions managed by the European Research Council. Other European funding programmes are managed by the European Science Foundation, the European University Institute, the European Association of National Metrology Institutes (EURAMET), etc.</p> <p>Many European countries have one or more national agencies responsible for research, science and/or technology development. The policies and mandates of these agencies will inevitably be different from country to country, but they are essential drivers of Open Science and it is vital for the EOSC to engage in a common platform with these stakeholders.</p>

Table 4: EOSC Stakeholders groups

The framework concentrates on three stakeholder *roles*, understanding that different stakeholders can play multiple roles, or different roles are different points in the research lifecycle or within their organisation. These are outlined in Table 5 (the stakeholders listed are indicative and not meant to be exhaustive or exclusive).

Primary Role	Description	Typical Stakeholders
Provider	Provides services, data or other resources (e.g. scientific instruments, training) into EOSC.	e-Infrastructures Enterprises Academic Institutions and Research Libraries Research Infrastructures VREs, and other H2020 Projects Other Service Providers
Consumer	Will make use of services, data, or other resources from EOSC.	Learned Societies, Research Communities, Scientific and Professional Associations Research Infrastructures Research Producing Organisations e-Infrastructures, VRE, and Other H2020 Projects Academic Institutions and Research Libraries Enterprises General Public
Decision-makers	Will be involved in the strategic direction, compliance and funding of EOSC.	National, Regional or Local Government Agencies Research Funding Bodies

Table 5: EOSC Primary Stakeholder Roles

In addition, there are some additional roles which are covered by the above stakeholders, but worth explicitly articulating – these are detailed in Table 6.

Supplementary Role	Description	Relationship to Primary Roles
Value-added providers	Many stakeholders (including e-infrastructures, research infrastructures, VREs etc.) will consume services and resources from some providers to provide value added services and resources to other consumers.	Within both Provider and Consumer roles
Funders	Provides funding for research on a local, national or international level	Sub-role within Decision-makers
Policy-makers	Regulates policy at a local, national or regional level.	Sub-role within Decision-makers

Table 6: EOSC Supplementary Stakeholder Roles